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ON-SITE JOURNAL REPAIR OF STEAM TURBINE ROTOR

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Abstract

The steam turbine rotor is the most important part of the steam turbine generator set. It will directly cause the rapid decrease of the output power or even paralysis of the whole unit just because of its high operation accuracy, fast operation speed and high manufacturing cost. Therefore, the repair of the rotor has become the most significant maintenance work of the power plant. In recent years, it is often found the entire ring of the rotor journal is worn and roughed during the on-site maintenance of the power plant. has to be studied how to achieve the on-site repair of the rotor journal and planned the process scheme which can be used in power plant immediately to protect the users' time cost and economic cost better.

In this paper, a variety of scientific research experiments have been carried out by the test boards made of 30Cr1Mo1V and 30Cr2Ni4MoV, which is the common material of the steam rotor with the precision cold repair welding machine for its welding ability, the reasonable range size and reasonable welding process scheme. What's more, simulation repair experiments have been carried out on the used rotor, with which the surface gap value and the result of the none destructive testing have been proven to fill the bill for the design requirements. And We finally get the ability to repair the rotor journal on site.

Keywords: steam turbine rotor; repair of the rotor journal on site; the precision cold repair welding machine.

1 Introduction

1.1 The main research content of this paper

This article aims to provide a repair process for the on-site micro-arc cold welding repair of steam turbine rotor journals in power plants. The welding experiments of 30Cr1Mo1V/30Cr2Ni4MoV materials are carried out to study its weldability, determine the reasonable defect repair size range and formulate reasonable welding process parameters. And finally realize the on-site repair of the rotor shaft diameter defect in the power plant [1].

1.2 Principle of precision cold repair welding machine

The precision repair welding technology is improved on the basis of traditional argon arc welding, and the welding power supply control system is upgraded to accurately control the output time of output peak current, current acceleration and braking time through electronic circuits, so as to realize the pulse square wave output of current and achieve thermal impact. Small, low temperature welding effect [2]. The

corresponding parameters can be set according to different welding repair requirements, and the repair welding accuracy is high.

The precision repair welding technology is relatively mature, the operation is less difficult, the heat input and welding undercut are small, and the product is small in size, easy to carry, and suitable for on-site journal repair.

1.3 Rework welding consumables selection

In this paper, the nickel-based welding consumable ERNiCrMo-3 (cold welding consumable) commonly used in the power industry is selected as the rework welding consumable. The selection basis for rework welding consumables is as follows:

1.3.1 Physical properties

① The thermal conductivity and linear expansion coefficient of nickel-based welding materials are close to those of iron-based materials, and the thermal stress is small during long-term high-temperature operation, so it can be used as welding materials for repairing rotor journals

② Because the nickel-based weld metal does not undergo phase change during the welding process and

there is no structural stress, usually neither preheating nor post-weld heat treatment is required, which not only simplifies the process, but also avoids excessive thermal effects. Thereby reducing deformation and residual stress [3].

③ Due to the low melting point of nickel-based welding materials, small thermal conductivity, weak

specification welding, and small heat-affected zone, at the same time repair welding is carried out slowly at room temperature, avoiding the thermal influence on the base metal, so that the welding stress and deformation are relatively low. small.

1.3.2 Mechanical properties

Table 1

Mechanical properties of commonly used rotor materials								
Material Grade	strength grade	RP0.2 N/mm2	Ra N/mm2	A4 %	Z %	Akv J	FATT50 °C	Upper platform energy J
30Cr1Mo1V	590	590-690	≥720	≥15	≥40	≥8	≤116	≥75
	620	620-720	≥720	≥19	≥59	≥108	≤-29	≥108
30Cr2Ni4MoV	690	690-790	≥790	≥18	≥56	≥95	≤-18	≥95

The mechanical properties of commonly used rotor materials are shown in the figure above. The commonly used strength grade of 30Cr2Ni4MoV is 760. It can be seen from Table 1.1 that the lower limit of the tensile strength of ERNiCrMo-3 after welding is 760MPa, and the tensile strength is usually ≥840MPa, which is close to the tensile strength of the above two materials., so the room temperature mechanical properties meet the requirements.

Based on the above reasons, ERNiCrMo-3 welding wire is selected as the welding material for rework.

2 Restoration test and process feasibility analysis

The test selects 30Cr1Mo1V and 30Cr2 Ni4MoV, which are commonly used materials for rotors, as the research objects, and uses the precision cold repair welding machine as the repair equipment to pass three types of simulation tests—butt test plate, U-shaped groove simulated roughening defect butt joint test, and surface surfacing test And relevant performance verification, and finally establish a feasible process plan [4]. The specific test protocol is shown below.

2.1 simulation test

2.1.1 Single side U-shaped groove with liner

It adopts the form of single U groove with liner [5], as shown in Figure 2.1 U -shaped groove processing diagram. After welding, PT and RT flaw detection are carried out. Samples are allowed to avoid defects. Samples are stretched, Bending and impact tests, and take metallographic samples, observe the three-zone metallographic phase (including tissue analysis, fusion and heat-affected zone thickness), and conduct three-zone hardness inspection on the metallographic sample.

Figure 1 U-shaped groove processing diagram

2.1.2 Butt joint test of R2 U-groove simulated nap defect

R2 and R4U-shaped grooves were processed on the test plate, as shown in Figure 2.2 R4 groove diagram. After the welding is completed, the thickness of the test plate is processed to 4mm, and the PT and RT flaw detections are carried out. The sample is allowed to avoid the defect sampling. (Including tissue analysis, fusion and heat-affected zone thickness).

Figure 2 R4 Groove Diagram

2.1.3 Surface welding test

According to NB/T 47014 surfacing welding standard for corrosion resistance, the surfacing layer requires 150mm long, 40mm wide and 5mm thick [6]. After surfacing, we carried out PT and RT flaw detection, and after passing the test, we carried out bending test, macroscopic and microscopic metallography (including three-zone structure analysis, fusion situation and heat-affected zone thickness), and chemical composition analysis (step test at intervals of 0.5 Determine the dilution rate of the weld according to the sample, the length of each step is 15-20mm), check the depth hardness of the surfacing layer (interval 0.5mm) (can be carried out on the layered chemical sample).

2.2 Test results and analysis

2.2.1 Tensile test results

Table 2

Tensile test results						
serial number	material	Joint form	tensile strength	standard value	percentage	
ZJDH19-Z-006	30Cr2Ni4MoV	docking	846	846	≥860	≥98%
ZJDH19-Z-004-1	30Cr2Ni4MoV	R2 groove surfacing	772	729	≥860	84%-90%
ZJDH19-Z-004-2	30Cr2Ni4MoV	R4 groove surfacing	833	769	≥860	89%-96%
ZJDH19-Z-005	30Cr1Mo1V	docking	874	875	≥720	qualified
ZJDH19-Z-003	30Cr1Mo1V	R2 groove surfacing	826	844	≥720	qualified

2.2.2 Layered chemical test results

The thickness of the surfacing layer is 4mm, and samples are taken at intervals of 0.4mm from the surface to check the dilution of the main chemical components such as Cr, Ni, Mo, Nb, Fe, etc., and it is found that

1. As the thickness of the surfacing layer increases, the original composition gradient of Fe

changes more obviously, and its dilution range is the largest.

2. The composition of the surfacing layer tends to be stable after the thickness of the surfacing layer is 0.8mm.

3. The thickness of the component mixing zone below the fusion line is about 0.8mm, which is consistent with the metallographic measurement results of the heat-affected zone.

Figure 3 Layered chemical test results

2.2.3 Hardness uniformity test

The thickness of the surfacing layer starts at 2.4mm, and the HV hardness value is measured at intervals of 0.2mm until 2mm below the fusion line. The hardness curve is drawn as follows: the heat-affected

zone is found to be less than 1mm, which is consistent with the metallographic test results [7]. The deviation of the hardness values of different thicknesses in the surfacing layer area is small, the uniformity is good, and the hardness of the heat-affected zone is higher.

Figure 4 Hardness test result

2.2.4 Metallographic anatomy test

Table 3

Metallographic test results				
serial number	Reinforcement mm	Penetration mm	Heat affected zone width mm	Defect situation
41	0.50	0.22-0.84	0.4-0.84	none
42	0.64	0.24-0.56	0.4-0.8	none
43	0.68	0.16-0.40	0.4-0.85	none
44	1.3	0.12-0.18	0.38-0.52	none
45	1.13	0.10-0.24	0.40-0.66	none

After metallographic dissection, observe the reinforcement, penetration depth, heat-affected zone width and defects as follows:

It is found that after welding with continuous pulse and precision pulse 135A current for a duration of 1300ms, the weld seam is well formed, the penetration depth and heat affected zone are small, and there are no defects in the joint surface and weld meat after welding. Using this current parameter can obtain the forming quality Good welds.

3 Summary

1. Through relevant experiments on 30Cr1Mo1V and 30Cr2Ni4MoV test plates, it is proved that the precision cold welding machine can obtain welded joints without undercuts, cracks and other defects, with good fusion, small heat- affected zone and dense structure.

2. After rework, the tensile strength and bending performance of the joint meet the requirements, and the hardness of the filling layer is uniform [8].

3. The design of the rotor journal requires radial runoff of 0.013mm, roundness of 0.02, and parallelism of 0.02. The repair effect of the rotor simulation is verified, and the flaw detection is qualified. After the undercut is repaired, the gap between the main body and the repaired surface is not more than 0.035mm.

4. After research, it is concluded that the repair defect size of this process method is the repair of point-like and non-intensive defects with a damage depth of <1.5mm, a width of <3mm, and a length of 2-3mm.

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